
Teaching English Action Verbs to Young EFL Learners Through Video-Based Instruction: A Quasi-Experimental Study

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Annotation *This research examines differences in teaching English action verbs to young EFL learners through video-based instruction compared to traditional methods. The study compares learning outcomes of students taught action verbs using videos with those who received traditional text-based instruction. A quasi-experimental research design was employed, involving an experimental and a control group. Participants were young learners aged 7–8 with beginner-level English proficiency (A1–A2), studying at private school “Ixlos” in Tashkent, Uzbekistan. Both groups completed pre-tests and post-tests to measure their knowledge of English action verbs. The experimental group received instruction supported by videos and visual demonstrations, while the control group was taught using traditional methods without video treatment. Reliability of the research instrument was checked through internal consistency analysis using JASP software. Results reveal that video-based instruction has a significant positive impact on students’ understanding and retention of English action verbs, contributing to improved vocabulary teaching strategies for young EFL learners and demonstrating the effectiveness of multimedia integration in foreign language education.*

Keywords *Action verbs, video-based instruction, young EFL learners, quasi-experimental design, vocabulary acquisition, multimedia learning, EFL teaching*

Yosh xorijiy til o‘rganuvchilariga inglizcha harakat fe‘llarini video asosidagi ta‘lim orqali o‘rgatish: kvazi-eksperimental tadqiqot

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Annotatsiya *Ushbu tadqiqot inglizcha harakat fe‘llarini 7–8 yoshli boshlang‘ich ingliz tili (EFL) o‘rganuvchilariga video asosidagi ta‘lim orqali o‘rgatishning an‘anaviy usul bilan solishtirilgan farqini o‘rgana di. Tadqiqot video yordamida harakat fe‘llari o‘rgatilgan o‘quvchilarning o‘quv natijalarini an‘anaviy matn asosidagi ta‘lim olgan o‘quvchilar bilan taqqoslashni maqsad qiladi. Kvazi-eksperimental tadqiqot dizaynidan foydalanilgan bo‘lib, eksperimental guruh va nazorat guruhini o‘z ichiga oladi. Ishtirokchilar A1–A2 darajasidagi ingliz tili bilimiga ega, 7–8 yoshli yosh o‘rganuvchilar bo‘lib, Toshkentdagi «Ixlos» xususiy maktabida tahsil oladi. Ikkala guruh ham harakat fe‘llari bilimini o‘lchash uchun oldingi test va keyingi testni topshirdi. Eksperimental guruh video va vizual ko‘rsatmalar yordamida ta‘lim oldi, nazorat guruhi esa an‘anaviy usulda o‘rgatildi. Tadqiqot ishonchiligi JASP dasturida ichki izchillik tahlili orqali tekshirildi. Natijalar shuni ko‘rsatadiki, video asosidagi ta‘lim o‘quvchilar harakat fe‘llari rini tushunishi va eslab qolishiga sezilarli ijobiy ta‘sir*

ko'rsatadi hamda yosh EFL o'rganuvchilari uchun lug'aviy o'rgatish strategiyalarini takomillashtirishga hissa qo'shadi.

Kalit so'zlar *Harakat fe'llari, video asosidagi ta'lim, yosh xorijiy til o'rganuvchilari, kvazi-eksperimental dizayn, lug'aviy o'zlashtirish, ko'p vositali ta'lim, ingliz tilini o'rgatish*

Обучение английским глаголам действия молодых учащихся посредством видеoinструкций: квазиэкспериментальное исследование

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Аннотация *Данное исследование изучает различия в обучении английским глаголам действия молодых учащихся, изучающих английский как иностранный язык, с применением видеoinструкций по сравнению с традиционными методами. Цель работы – сравнить результаты обучения учащихся, которых учили глаголам действия с использованием видеоматериалов, с результатами тех, кто получал традиционное текстовое обучение. Применялся квазиэкспериментальный дизайн исследования, включавший экспериментальную и контрольную группы. Участниками стали дети 7–8 лет с начальным уровнем владения английским языком (A1–A2), обучающиеся в частной школе «Ихлос» в Ташкенте, Узбекистан. Обе группы прошли предварительное и итоговое тестирование. Экспериментальная группа получала инструкции с видеоподдержкой, контрольная группа обучалась по традиционным методикам. Надёжность инструмента проверялась посредством анализа внутренней согласованности в программе JASP. Результаты показывают, что видеообучение оказывает значительное положительное влияние на понимание и запоминание учащимися глаголов действия и вносит вклад в совершенствование стратегий обучения иностранному языку.*

Ключевые слова *Глаголы действия, видеообучение, молодые учащиеся ИЯ, квазиэкспериментальный дизайн, усвоение словарного запаса, мультимедийное обучение, преподавание английского языка*

Introduction

Vocabulary acquisition is a central aspect of second language learning, particularly for young learners who are at the early stages of English language development. Vocabulary knowledge enables learners to understand spoken and written language and to express their ideas effectively. Among various

categories of vocabulary, action verbs are especially important because they are used frequently in daily communication and help learners describe movements, activities, and routines. For young EFL learners, mastering action verbs is essential for building basic sentence structures and developing communicative competence.

However, teaching action verbs to young learners can be challenging when instruction relies mainly on traditional methods such as textbooks, translations, and verbal explanations. Children aged 7–8 are still developing their cognitive and language abilities, and they often learn more effectively through concrete experiences rather than abstract explanations. As a result, purely text-based instruction may limit learners' understanding and retention of new vocabulary, including action verbs.

In recent years, the integration of technology in education has transformed language teaching practices. One widely used technological tool in English language teaching is video. Videos combine visual, auditory, and sometimes kinesthetic elements, allowing learners to see actions performed while hearing the corresponding words. This multisensory input can make learning more meaningful and engaging for young learners. Video-based instruction also supports different learning styles and can increase learners' motivation, attention, and participation in the classroom.

For young EFL learners, videos provide a clear and contextualized representation of action verbs, helping them to associate words with actions more easily. When learners observe actions in videos and repeat them, they are more likely to understand the meaning of the verbs and remember them over time. Additionally, video-based lessons can create a more enjoyable learning environment, which is particularly important for maintaining young learners' interest and reducing anxiety in language learning.

Therefore, this study aims to investigate whether there is a difference in teaching English action verbs through video-based instruction compared to traditional text-based methods. By employing a quasi-experimental design with an experimental and a control group, the study seeks to determine whether video-based instruction leads to different learning outcomes in terms of young learners'

knowledge of action verbs. The findings may provide practical implications for EFL teachers and contribute to the development of more effective vocabulary teaching strategies for young learners.

Literature review

Vocabulary acquisition is a fundamental aspect of second language learning, as it directly influences learners' ability to comprehend and produce language. Nation (2001) emphasizes the importance of vocabulary by arguing that without grammar very little can be conveyed, but without vocabulary nothing can be conveyed at all. This highlights the central role of vocabulary in communication. For young EFL learners, vocabulary learning is especially important because it forms the foundation for further language development.

Young learners acquire language differently from adults, as they rely more on sensory input and concrete experiences. Cameron (2001) explains that children learn language through seeing, hearing, touching, and doing, which suggests that vocabulary instruction should involve visual and physical support. This is particularly relevant when teaching action verbs, as these words describe observable movements and actions. When learners can see and perform an action, they are more likely to understand and remember the corresponding verb.

Traditional vocabulary teaching methods often focus on written forms, translation, and teacher explanation. While these approaches may help learners recognise words, they can be less effective for young learners who struggle with abstract instruction. Cameron (2001) argues that young learners benefit most from learning activities that are meaningful and connected to real-life experiences rather than isolated word lists. Therefore, relying solely on text-based instruction may limit vocabulary retention and engagement.

In response to these challenges, researchers have highlighted the benefits of multimedia and video-based instruction in

language learning. Mayer (2009), in his Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning, argues that people learn more deeply from words and pictures than from words alone. Video-based instruction combines visual and auditory input, allowing learners to process information through multiple channels. This can reduce cognitive load and enhance understanding, especially for young learners.

Similarly, Paivio (1986) proposed the Dual Coding Theory, which suggests that information presented both visually and verbally is more easily remembered. According to Paivio (1986), memory is improved when information is encoded in both verbal and non-verbal systems simultaneously. When action verbs are taught through video, learners can associate the word with a visual representation of the action, which strengthens memory and recall.

Several studies have demonstrated positive effects of video use in vocabulary instruction. Berk (2009) notes that videos can increase students' attention, motivation, and engagement, making them particularly effective for young learners. In the context of action verbs, videos allow learners to observe movements, imitate actions, and actively participate in the learning process, which supports deeper understanding.

However, researchers also caution that videos must be used purposefully. Mayer (2009) emphasises that multimedia instruction is most effective when learners are actively engaged rather than passively watching. This means videos should be integrated with activities such as repetition, physical response, and practice tasks to maximise learning outcomes.

Despite strong theoretical support for video-based instruction, relatively few studies focus specifically on teaching English action verbs to young EFL learners using video. This indicates a gap in the existing literature. The present study aims to address this gap by examining whether teaching action verbs

through video leads to better learning outcomes compared to traditional text-based instruction.

Methods

Research Design

The study investigated whether there is a difference between students who learned action verbs through video-based instruction and students who received no video treatment in regard to their knowledge of English action verbs. The independent variable was the instructional method (video-based vs. traditional), and the dependent variable was students' action verb test scores. The research employed a *quasi-experimental design* with two groups: an experimental group (video-based instruction) and a control group (traditional instruction).

Null hypothesis: *There will be no significant difference between students who learned through video and students who received no video treatment in regard to their knowledge of English action verbs.*

Alternative hypothesis: *There will be a significant difference in the test results of students who learned through video-based instruction compared to those who received traditional instruction.*

Participants

The research involved 50 elementary school pupils from private school "Ixlos" in Chilonzor district, Tashkent, including both male and female learners from 1st and 2nd grades. All participants are native Uzbek speakers who have been learning English as a foreign language for approximately two years within the educational curriculum. Their overall English proficiency level was estimated to be within the A1–A2 range according to CEFR standards. The students shared comparable educational backgrounds and were taught according to the same state-approved English curricula. All pupils possess basic literacy skills and demonstrate familiarity with elementary English vocabulary, simple sentence patterns, and common classroom instructions.

The quasi-experimental design included two independent groups of 25 students each. The experimental group received instruction through short action verb videos, acquiring knowledge via audio-visual input. The control group was taught in the traditional way: action verb words were written on the board with their Uzbek translation, without the use of any visual aids or multimedia materials. Since the two mean scores derived from the two independent groups involved no matching or pairing, an *independent samples t-test* was identified as the most appropriate statistical procedure.

The research took place over two weeks, comprising six class hours (three hours per week). The first class was dedicated to the pre-test, the middle four lessons were used for instruction, and the sixth class was dedicated to the post-test.

Research Instruments

To address the research question, two main instruments were used: pre-tests and post-tests, along with lesson plans for both teaching methods. The tests were designed to measure learners' understanding and use of action verbs before and after the instructional intervention. Each test consisted of 15 matching items used to assess students' knowledge of the action verbs taught during the experiment. The tests were researcher-designed based on CEFR A1–A2 level tasks. Multimedia tools (videos) and the *Family and Friends* textbook were selected according to research objectives. The post-test employed a similar matching activity, and all results were calculated to assess learners' awareness of action verbs.

Scoring Procedures

The tests were scored using a dichotomous coding system: 1 point for each correct answer and 0 for each incorrect answer. The maximum possible score was 15 out of 15 items. Inter-rater reliability was ensured by using three independent raters to mark the tests.

Results

Descriptive Statistics

A total of 50 students participated in the research, with 25 students in the experimental group and 25 in the control group. All students took part in both the pre-test and post-test. In the pre-test, the mean score of the control group was 6.00, while the experimental group's mean score was 7.68. In the post-test, the control group averaged 9.88, while the experimental group achieved 11.12.

Regarding minimum scores, in the pre-test the control group scored 2.00 and the experimental group scored 4.00; in the post-test, both groups' minimum scores were 8.00. Regarding maximum scores, the control group received 10.00 in the pre-test and 13.00 in the post-test, while the experimental group received 12.00 in the pre-test and 15.00 in the post-test.

Inferential Statistics

An independent samples *t-test* was conducted to compare the mean scores of the two groups on both the pre-test and post-test. For the pre-test, results showed a statistically significant difference between the groups, $t(48) = -2.944$, $p = .005$. For the post-test, there was also a statistically significant difference, $t(48) = -2.537$, $p = .014$, suggesting that the difference between the groups was maintained after the intervention.

Assumption checks were conducted prior to interpreting the results. The Shapiro–Wilk test indicated that the pre-test scores were normally distributed ($W = 0.984$, $p = .727$), while the post-test scores showed a statistically significant deviation from normality ($W = 0.949$, $p = .030$). Levene's test for equality of variances was satisfied for the pre-test ($p = .605$) but was significant for the post-test ($p = .012$), indicating unequal variances between groups. Therefore, Welch's *t-test* is a more appropriate procedure for analysing the post-test results.

Overall, the experimental group demonstrated higher mean scores than the control group in both the pre-test and post-

test. Following the intervention, the experimental group showed substantially greater improvement compared to the control group, suggesting a positive effect of video-based instruction on learners' knowledge of English action verbs.

Discussion

The primary aim of this quasi-experimental study was to investigate the effect of video-based instruction compared to traditional text-based methods on the acquisition of English action verbs among young EFL learners. The results, analysed through independent samples *t*-tests, provide meaningful insights into the effectiveness of multimedia integration in vocabulary teaching.

The descriptive statistics reveal a clear pattern. Before the intervention (pre-test), the experimental group already had a higher mean score (7.68) than the control group (6.00), and this difference was statistically significant ($p = .005$). After the instructional period, both groups showed improvement, but the experimental group taught with videos achieved a higher mean score (11.12) compared to the control group (9.88). The *t*-test confirmed this difference was also statistically significant ($p = .014$), suggesting that video-based instruction contributed to superior learning outcomes in the post-test.

It is important to interpret these results while considering the assumption checks. For the post-test, Levene's test was significant ($p = .012$), indicating a violation of the equal variances assumption, which means the variability in scores differed between the two groups after the treatment. Importantly, the experimental group achieved a significantly higher mean score, supporting the conclusion that video-based instruction was an effective treatment. These findings are consistent with those of Mayer (2009), who argues that multimedia learning facilitates deeper cognitive processing, and Berk (2009), who highlights the motivational benefits of video in educational settings. The results also align with

Paivio (1986), whose Dual Coding Theory predicts stronger recall when information is presented through both verbal and visual channels.

Conclusion

The main aim of this research was to investigate the effectiveness of video-based instruction compared to traditional text-based methods in teaching action verbs to young EFL learners aged 7–8 years. Using a quasi-experimental design with an experimental group (video-based instruction) and a control group (traditional instruction), the study sought to determine whether video-based teaching had a significant effect on young learners' comprehension and retention of English action verbs.

The results showed that video-based instruction significantly enhanced the vocabulary development of young learners. The experimental group achieved greater post-test gains compared to the control group, confirming the effectiveness of multimedia-supported language teaching. These findings align with the theoretical frameworks proposed by Mayer (2009) and Paivio (1986), which emphasise the advantages of dual-channel processing in learning, as well as with the empirical work of Berk (2009) and the foundational perspective of Nation (2001) on the centrality of vocabulary in language acquisition.

The practical significance of the study is relevant for foreign language teachers, curriculum designers, and education policymakers. Video-based instruction can be an effective tool for making vocabulary lessons more engaging, meaningful, and accessible for young learners (Cameron, 2001). This method accommodates different learning styles, increases participation, and maintains motivation among beginner-level students.

In conclusion, video-based instruction is a promising pedagogical approach for teaching action verbs to young foreign language learners. By purposefully integrating video

materials into language classrooms, teachers can create effective and engaging learning

environments that are responsive to the developmental needs of young learners.

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